

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Portugal

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

Author(s):

Isabel Caetano, ORCID [0000-0001-7972-7787](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7972-7787)

Filipa Pereira, ORCID [0000-0002-5732-9996](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5732-9996)

This work is supported by a cooperative agreement (DE-SC0021915) under the U.S. Department of Energy Office of Science.

About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the World Data System (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

Suggested Citation:

Caetano, I., & Pereira, F. (2025). Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Portugal. Scientific Data Repository-related Policies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17236559>

Table of Contents

Acronyms.....	2
Introduction.....	3
Brief overview of the Portuguese research landscape.....	3
Research Data Management.....	4
Reserach Data Repositories.....	5
References.....	9

Acronyms

CRIS	Current Research Information System
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FCT	Foundation for Science and Technology
RCAAP	Scientific Open Access Repositories of Portugal

Introduction

Open science enhances scientific collaboration, improves the quality of scientific results, and promotes the dissemination of knowledge, thereby making science more inclusive and transparent.

The management and sharing of research data is essential in the practice of open science, as it helps to ensure that research results are validated and can be reused, thus accelerating the dissemination of scientific knowledge.

Effective research and innovation systems are characterized by an open, interconnected, and synergistic operational model, supported by a strong capacity to absorb knowledge and implement best practices. In Portugal, the research community is progressively engaging in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), notably through increasing participation in infraEOSC Projects and active involvement in several national nodes of international initiatives.

The Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) is a national public agency that supports research in science, technology, and innovation, covering all areas of knowledge. It is a special regime public institute under the supervision and oversight of the Ministry of Education, Science, and Innovation.

As the national funding entity, FCT is committed to adopting instruments that promote the practice of open science within the framework of the scientific activity it funds (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT)).

Brief overview of the Portuguese research landscape

Portugal's scientific system has seen remarkable growth, particularly over the last two decades. This is evident in the substantial increase in total expenditure on R&D, which has risen from €1.038 billion in 2021 to €4.5 billion in 2023, representing 1.70% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Direção-Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência et al., 2024). Similarly, the number of researchers has surged significantly, from 17,725 Full-Time Equivalent (FTE) researchers in 2021 to 62,476 FTE researchers in 2023 (Direção-Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência et al., 2024).

According to the latest European Innovation Scoreboard (European Commission, 2024), Portugal's performance in research and innovation framework conditions for 2024 positions its research system at 115.7% of the EU average, while human resources stand at 97.6% of the EU average. Noteworthy improvements since 2017 include a 60.2 percent increase in international scientific co-publications and a 75.8 percentage point rise in the percentage of foreign doctorate students. These positive trends are significant strengths; however, they also present challenges, particularly the need to support the expanding number of research actors and their respective growth strategies, as well as to create attractive conditions for future development.

Currently, Portugal boasts more than 100 higher education institutions, 312 R&D units, 40 associate labs, and 41 collaborative labs, in addition to other types of R&D performers (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT), 2024a, 2024b, 2024c). Given this extensive landscape, the quality and management of data are critical to maximizing the value generated.

Research Data Management

FCT encourages researchers to adopt good research data management practices and to share their results with the scientific community. In this sense, FCT has adopted a policy on the availability of data and other results of funded scientific research, which came into force in May 2014 (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT), 2014).

The commitment to the general principles of FAIR research data (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), the requirements of important funding frameworks (such as Horizon Europe), the alignment with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the recommendations of Science Europe on research data management (Science Europe, 2018), and the UNESCO's recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021) contributed to a revision of the current policy.

A new policy on the management and sharing of data resulting from FCT funded research, outlining clear principles and requirements, is expected to be introduced to the community in early 2025. This forthcoming policy will align with the standards of major funding agencies and reference entities. Key provisions include:

- **Submission of a Data Management Plan (DMP):** A DMP must be submitted within six months of the grant's start date, based on a specific template.
- **Deposit of Research Data:** Researchers are required to deposit research data in a trustworthy repository (e.g., registered in a global directory of repositories, and/or aggregated in OpenAIRE, and/or certified).

- Use of Persistent Identifiers and Standard Licenses: These should ensure that third parties are able to access, extract, exploit, reproduce and disseminate results, free of charge.
- Reuse of data: Information, via the repository, on the tools and instruments needed to validate or reuse the data available (and, whenever possible, provide the tools and instruments themselves).

These requirements reflect and promote, in fact, the best practices in research data management.

Research Data Repositories

To support the beneficiaries who do not have an option to deposit their research data, FCT has been developing a research data repository, named Polen Repository (Repositório Polen), which is currently in its pilot phase of implementation. Seven national institutions/projects, focused on various scientific domains, are participating in this pilot phase, with the aim of testing and validating important functionalities, as well as ensuring that the community's concerns about data sharing are covered.

This repository will be a long-tail and multi-disciplinary repository that aims to meet the following needs:

- Promoting the adoption of open-science practices and compliance with the general principles of FAIR research data;
- Supporting the deposit, preservation, and safeguarding of the research data resulting from funded projects;
- Ensuring the compliance with the requirements of FCT's data policy (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT));
- Supporting the adoption of Portugal's Current Research Information System (Portugal Current Research Information System (PTCRIS), 2019) regulatory framework;
- Integrating with the Scientific Open Access Repositories of Portugal (Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal (RCAAP));
- Integrating with the EOSC partnership.

However, the growing importance of open science and data sharing has driven the development and a progressive increase in the number of data repositories in Portugal. These repositories serve as critical infrastructures for storing, preserving, and disseminating research outputs across various scientific and technological domains.

Similarly to the Polen Repository, these institutional services intend to serve their own community of users, ensuring the research data management best practices. Managed by universities, research institutes, and collaborative organizations, these platforms support compliance with funder requirements, enhance data accessibility, and promote interdisciplinary collaboration.

To further advance these goals, a working group mobilized by the scientific community (Grupo Repositórios de Dados: Tecnologia, organização e certificação) is addressing critical topics related to research data repositories. The group's primary objectives are to:

- Support researchers in publishing research data;
- Propose training initiatives and develop support documentation;
- Enhance repository interoperability and establish seamless system connections.

As part of this initiative, various institutions have showcased their repositories and shared insights into their unique objectives and contributions (Fórum de Gestão de Dados de Investigação). The following table summarizes these use cases, providing a comprehensive view of the repositories' roles in supporting research and innovation across Portugal.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Portugal

Name of repository	Entity	Main scope and objectives	Science&Technology domains	Date of launch
INESC TEC Data Repository	INESC TEC	Platform that showcases datasets produced or used by INESC TEC researchers and their partners. Research Data Management/Development of RDM plans	AI; Bioengineering; Robotics, Energy; Computer Science; Engineering	2017
ISCTE Repository	ISCTE	Preservation, Dissemination and Access to intellectual production.	SSH; Business and Management; Political science; Sociology and Public Policies; Communication&Marketing; Digital technologies; Data Science; Architecture; ITC	2006
DataRepositóriUM	Universidade do Minho	a) Deposit files in organized datasets and collections; b) Preserve files and datasets; c) Support compliance with funders' requirements; d) Register persistent identifiers (DOI); e) Allow controlled access with prior identification; f) Associate reuse licenses and make usage terms explicit; g) Document datasets with disciplinary metadata; h) Facilitate the dissemination of research results; i) Enable the citation of data and credit to producers, and j) Facilitate the provision of data to publishers.	Multidisciplinary focus	2020
Dados.IPB	Instituto Politécnico de Bragança	To store, preserve, and make available the research data generated by the IPB research centers and also by the collaborative laboratories. The objectives are: to deposit files (datasets) in communities; preserve the datasets and metadata; comply with funders' requirements; use persistent identifiers such as DOI; facilitate the provision of data to publishers; and allow controlled access to datasets that are under restricted access.	Multidisciplinary focus	2023
Portuguese Node of GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	Instituto Superior de Agronomia	Promote the integration of Portuguese data providers and biodiversity information resources into the GBIF network, and the availability of biodiversity data for scientific research and societal use.	Biodiversity; Environment; Natural resources; Sustainable development; Biosafety; Invasive species; Habitat restoration	2015
DMPortal BioData.pt	BioData.pt Association	Elixir Portuguese Node	Life Sciences; Health; Marine Bio Data; Plant Bio Data;	2023
COI Catalogue Herbarium	Universidade de Coimbra	Platform to retrieve information on COI specimens. The herbarium of the University of Coimbra is the largest Portuguese herbarium, housing approximately 800 000 specimens of plants, fungi, algae and lichens. The dataset, digitised collection of the Herbarium, is available through GBIF.	Life Sciences	2020
Hidrográfico+	Instituto Hidrográfico	A geospatial infrastructure of marine data created to facilitate citizen access to data produced by the Hydrographic Institute, fostering ocean knowledge and science, promoting awareness of the importance of the oceans, boosting the blue economy, and contributing to ocean sustainability and societal development. A node of the community of Portuguese Marine Data Providers.	Marine Geology; Hydrography; Oceanography; Chemistry&Marine Pollution; Navigation Safety	2018
DUnAS	Universidade de Aveiro	Repository designed for the archiving, publication, and access to research data generated within the scope of the scientific and academic activities of the University of Aveiro (UA). Serving an institution that teaches and conducts research across multiple fields of knowledge, DUnAS is an institutional and multidisciplinary repository.	Multidisciplinary focus	2022

Source: Fórum GDI, 2024

Table 1 - National research data repositories use cases

Portuguese research data repositories reflect the country's commitment to advancing scientific knowledge, fostering global collaboration and promoting the adoption of best practices. These platforms support diverse scientific domains and enable institutions to share research outputs, enhance data accessibility, and ensure long-term preservation in alignment with open science principles.

From biodiversity and life sciences to engineering and oceanography, these repositories cater to a wide range of research fields, enabling researchers and institutions to share their findings on a global scale. The repositories also play a crucial role in fostering innovation, ensuring data preservation, and facilitating the reuse of datasets in both academic and industrial contexts. Therefore, it could be considered a priority to promote the use and alignment of practices in these services.

References

BioData. BioData.pt Data Management Portal <https://dmportal.biodata.pt>

Direção-Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência, Direção de Serviços de Estatística da Ciência e Tecnologia e da Sociedade de Informação, & Equipa para a Monitorização da Investigação e Desenvolvimento. (2024). Inquérito ao Potencial Científico e Tecnológico Nacional (IPCTN) - Resultados provisórios 2023. Retrieved 29 January 2025 from <https://www.dgeec.medu.pt/api/ficheiros/669ede41d7027deffdb15ce5>

EOSC. European Open Science Cloud. Retrieved 29 January 2025 from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

European Commission. (2024). European Innovation Scoreboard 2024 Country Profile Portugal. Retrieved 23 January 2025 from https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/eis/2024/ec_rtd_eis-country-profile-pt.pdf

Fórum de Gestão de Dados de Investigação (2024). Repositórios de Dados - Casos de Estudo. <https://zenodo.org/communities/forumgdi/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT). (17 April 2024). Open Science Policies. Retrieved 19 January 2025 <https://www.fct.pt/en/sobre/politicas-e-estrategias/politicas-de-ciencia-aberta/>

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT). (2014). Política sobre a Disponibilização de Dados e outros Resultados de Projetos de I&D Financiados Pela FCT. Retrieved 16 January 2025 from https://www.fct.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/PoliticaAcessoAberto_Dados.pdf

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT). (2024a, 20 June 2024). Laboratórios Associados. Retrieved 30 January 2025 from <https://www.fct.pt/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/instituicoes-de-id/laboratorios-associados/>

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT). (2024b, 20 June 2024). Laboratórios Colaborativos. Retrieved 30 January 2025 from <https://www.fct.pt/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/instituicoes-de-id/laboratorios-colaborativos/>

- Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT). (2024c, 20 June 2024). Unidades de I&D. Retrieved 30 January 2025, from <https://www.fct.pt/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/instituicoes-de-id/unidades-de-id/>
- Global Biodiversity Information Facility - PORTUGAL. (2015). Portal de Dados de Biodiversidade de Portugal. <https://www.gbif.pt/?language=en>
- Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, T. a. S. I. INESC TEC Research Data Repository. <https://rdm.inesctec.pt/>
- Instituto Hidrográfico. Hidrográfico+. <https://geomar.hidrografico.pt/>
- Instituto Politécnico de Bragança. Instituto Politecnico de Bragança Repositório de Dados. <https://dados.ipb.pt/>
- ISCTE - University Institute of Lisbon. ISCTE Repository <https://repositorio.iscte-iul.pt/>
Portugal Current Research Information System (PTCRIS). (2019). Quadro Normativo. Retrieved 16 January 2025, from <https://ptcris.pt/quadro-normativo-2/>
- Repositório Polen. Repositório Polen. <https://repositorio.polen.fccn.pt/>
- Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal (RCAAP). <https://www.rcaap.pt/>
- Science Europe. (2018). Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management. Retrieved 16 January 2025, from https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/jezkhnoo/se_rdm_practical_guide_final.pdf
- UNESCO. (2021). Recommendation on Open Science [programme and meeting document]. 34. Retrieved 29 January 2025, from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>
- Universidade do Minho. Repositório de Dados da Universidade do Minho. <https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt>
- University Aveiro. DUnAs. <https://dunas.ua.pt/>
- University of Coimbra. COI CATALOGUE Herbarium of University of Coimbra. <https://coicatalogue.uc.pt>

World Data System International Program Office

1345 Circle Park Drive
Communications Building
Knoxville, TN 37996-0341
01-865-974-2156

Email: wds-ipo@utk.edu
Website: worlddatasystem.org
Instagram: [@wds_ipo](https://www.instagram.com/wds_ipo)
LinkedIn: [@company/world-data-system](https://www.linkedin.com/company/world-data-system)
X (formerly Twitter): [@ISC_WDS](https://twitter.com/ISC_WDS)
Vimeo: [@worlddatasystem](https://vimeo.com/worlddatasystem)

**International
Science Council**